

“IMPROVING THE METHOD OF FORMING A GEODATABASE OF SETTLEMENT LANDS”

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ABSTRACT

this scientific article focuses on the issues of forming the account of residential arrays and determining periodic changes in the geodatabase. A scientific result dedicated to the automation of the system for determining the dynamics of their change is listed on the basis of the algorithm for remote study of settlements using software in the Geoinformation system category.

The boundaries of settlements - located in the territory of cities, towns, villages, these are the external boundaries of the lands of settlements that distinguish lands from other lands, and the software of geographic information systems is widely used to analyze land use and determine changes in the lands of settlements.

In order to take into account the plots of land in the settlement, their effective use and protection, buildings and structures belonging to the plot of land are also formed on the geodatabase. In this regard, the data of the state cadastre of buildings and structures in the geodatabase are recorded, as in attributive data, property rights to buildings and structures or other material rights (emergence, transfer to another person, restriction and termination), as well as other information describing the object.

Other technical data on the parameters of buildings and structures (floors, general, residential, production areas), occupied land plot, construction date, availability of engineering and technical communications, seismic resistance and attributive data of buildings and structures. the settlement was formed on land.

Each building and structure is considered as a whole with plots of land by its significance, only when analyzing buildings and structures they are divided into liters, in general, they are taken into account together with the plot of land on which buildings and structures are located, that is, the number of real estate located in the settlement is taken in relation to the plot

As a result of scientific research, processes were carried out in ArcGIS software to process the results of a field study, to integrate the calculations analyzes carried out in the field into the geodatabase in the form of a vector layer, to separate real estate objects and user indicators from real estate objects. The lands of settlements have been geovisualized using geostatistical analysis. In addition, cartography, cadastre and land registration of settlements have been modernized. This created a cartographic basis for defining the boundaries of administrative-territorial units, conducting land management, creating agricultural maps of 1:10000 and 1:25000 scale in cases of illegal land use, as well as electronic maps of settlements of 1:2000 scale.

Modern technologies for the formation of a geographical information base

To improve the methodology for the formation of GIB (geographical information base), modern technologies are used to improve the accuracy, efficiency and effectiveness of work with land resources. The main technologies include:

1. Geographic Information Systems (GIS):

- Creation and management of data: GIS allows you to collect, store, analyze and visualize spatial information about land plots.
- Integration with other data: the ability to combine data from different sources, such as cadastral maps, satellite images and demographic data.

2. Remote sensing:

- Satellite images: using satellite images to monitor changes in land use and assess its condition.
- Aerial photography: the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to capture very detailed images of the area.

3. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS):

- A Precise positioning: GNSS provides high accuracy in determining the coordinates of land plots important for inventory and monitoring.

4. Automated data management systems:

- Large data processing: using Big Data Technologies to analyze large amounts of spatial data.
- Machine learning and artificial intelligence: using machine learning algorithms to automate the process of data analysis and pattern recognition.

Based on the requirements of today, geoinformation technology programs are being improved in the world, and modern geoinformation technology programs are being used in our country among the developed countries of the world, and high results are being achieved in the republic in the introduction of geoinformation technologies. The tasks of the development of territories for the effective use, accounting and protection of land are defined.

Improving the methodology for the formation of the geographic information base of the lands of settlements is an important step towards a more efficient and rational use of land resources. Modern technologies such as GIS, remote sensing and GNSS open up new possibilities for improving the accuracy and efficiency of ground control. The introduction of standardization, automation and data integration, as well as the development of information infrastructure and professional development of specialists contribute to the achievement of sustainable and effective management of territorial resources.

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